

Coherent light emission in cathodoluminescence when using GaAs in a scanning (transmission) electron microscope

Michael Stöger-Pollach^{a,b,*}, Cornelia F. Pichler^b, Topa Dan^c, Gregor A. Zickler^d,
Kristýna Bukvišová^e, Oliver Eibl^{a,b}, Franz Brandstätter^c

^a University Service Centre for Transmission Electron Microscopy (USTEM), Technische Universität Wien, Wiedner Hauptstraße 8-10, 1040 Wien, Austria

^b Institute for Solid State Physics, Technische Universität Wien, Wiedner Hauptstraße 8-10, 1040 Wien, Austria

^c Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Burgring 7, 1010 Wien, Austria

^d Department for Chemistry and Physics of Materials, Paris Lodron Universität Salzburg, Jakob-Haringer Str. 2A, 5020 Salzburg, Austria

^e Central European Institute of Technology (CEITEC), Brno University of Technology, Purkyňova 123, Brno 612 00, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

For most materials science oriented applications incoherent cathodoluminescence (CL) is of main interest, for which the recombination of electron-hole pairs yields the emission of light. However, the incoherent signal is superimposed by coherently excited photons, similar to the situation for X-rays in Energy-Dispersive X-ray spectra (EDX). In EDX two very different processes superimpose in each spectrum: Bremsstrahlung and characteristic X-ray radiation. Both processes yield X-rays, however, their origin is substantially different. Therefore, in the present CL study we focus on the coherent emission of light, in particular Čerenkov radiation. We use a 200 μm thick GaAs sample, not electron transparent and therefore not acting as a light guide, and investigate the radiation emitted from the top surface of the sample generated by back-scattered electrons on their way out of the specimen. The CL spectra revealed a pronounced peak corresponding to the expected interband transition. This peak was at 892 nm at room temperature and shifted to 845 nm at 80 K. The coherent light emission significantly modifies the shape of CL spectra at elevated beam energies. For the first time, by the systematic variation of current and energy of primary electrons we could distinguish the coherent and incoherent light superimposed in CL spectra. These findings are essential for the correct interpretation of CL spectra in STEM. The Čerenkov intensity as well as the total intensity in a spectrum scales linearly with the beam current. Additionally, we investigate the influence of asymmetric mirrors on the spectral shapes, collecting roughly only half of the whole solid angle. Different emission behaviour of different physical causes thus lead to changes in the overall spectral shape.

1. Introduction

Micro-characterization of semiconductors is a quickly improving topic in actual research in order to satisfy the increasing needs of high-performance materials for many different applications. In this context, cathodoluminescence (CL) is an interesting technique for studying defect states in electronic devices. In general, CL in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) is the method of choice [1], sometimes CL in a (scanning) transmission electron microscope (S/TEM) is used [2]. CL is particularly used to provide important information on the luminosity such as optical properties and doping or defect levels in GaAs, GaN and related films [1,3].

In the present work we use both, CL combined with SEM and CL combined with S/TEM. The prior set-up is used for general investigations in the range of beam energies being usually employed in CL

investigations of semiconductors. The S/TEM is taken for higher beam energies in order to intensify coherently emitted radiation caused by the Čerenkov effect [4–6] and transition radiation [7–9].

One aim of the present work is to figure out, that the interpretation of CL spectra recorded by employing SEM is more delicious as thought until now. In actually most common experimental set-ups it is nearly impossible to distinguish between incoherent and coherent signals [10], because both are contributing to the overall CL intensity in the same frequency range. The main difference can be found in the angular emission profiles [10,11]. Usually collector systems are applied, which are integrating over a certain angular range. This is because one needs to generate enough signal strength on the detector for improving the signal to noise ratio. Due to the angular integration, the physical reason

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: stoeger@ustem.tuwien.ac.at (M. Stöger-Pollach).

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Table 1

Čerenkov limit for selected semiconductors and insulators. The reference is with respect to the refractive index n .

	n	c_n (m/s)	E_{max} (keV)	Reference
Ge	5.06	59 224 112	10.27	[14]
Si	4.123	72 712 213	15.73	[14]
GaAs	4.1	73 120 111	15.91	[15]
InP	3.68	81 421 091	19.95	[14]
GaP	3.47	86 395 521	22.63	[14]
CdTe	3.05	98 292 609	29.9	[16]
GaN	2.42	123 881 181	50.15	[17]
HfO ₂	2.12	141 411 537	68.52	[18]
Si ₃ N ₄	2.06	145 884 408	73.93	[19]
Al ₂ O ₃	1.77	169 374 270	108.31	[20]
SiO ₂	1.46	205 337 300	190.33	[21]

of the respective intensities is kept hidden. The second aim of the present study is being even more important. It is to characterize the spectral contributions of coherent and incoherent emission processes. In order to prevent the CL spectra from being altered by light guiding modes and Fabry–Perot interference effects [5,6], we simplified the sample geometry and use a 200 μm thick GaAs sample being not electron transparent. We study the effects of coherent and incoherent light emission in the case of GaAs, because this material shows a strong transition at approximately 890 nm wavelength (at room temperature). Additionally it has a broad peak at shorter wavelengths, which is thought to be in relation with defect states generated by electron irradiation [3] and crystal growth techniques [12,13].

2. Coherent light emission

Coherent light emission under electron irradiation is caused by the excitation of Čerenkov photons and by the excitation of Transition radiation. Whereas the latter is a non-relativistic effect the prior appears as soon as the speed of a charged particle (electron) v_{e^-} exceeds the phase velocity of light inside the medium c_n .

$$v_{e^-} \geq c_n = \frac{c}{n(\lambda)}, \quad (1)$$

with c as the vacuum speed of light and $n(\lambda)$ as the wavelength dependent refractive index of the medium. Hence, the Čerenkov limit (E_{max}) can be calculated using

$$E_{max} = m_e c^2 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{c_n}{c}\right)^2}} - 1 \right). \quad (2)$$

Table 1 gives the Čerenkov limits E_{max} at 540 nm wavelength for selected semiconductors and insulators. In conventional SEMs, having a maximum beam energy of 30 keV, all materials listed in the table below CaTe can be anyhow studied without the excitation of Čerenkov photons. As soon as materials are studied by employing CL in a STEM, the beam energy becomes relevant for all materials.

Up to now, coherent light emission was not considered when trying to interpret CL spectra. Additionally, any emitted light (coherently or incoherently generated) might be reflected inside the sample at interfaces and at lattice defects [5,6] due to the abrupt change of the local optical properties. In the present paragraph we discuss how coherently excited light is able to leave the sample surface in backward direction being opposite to the direction of the electron beam.

There are two dominant mechanisms of coherently emitted light in a SEM: Transition radiation and Čerenkov radiation. Whereas the prior has little intensity in semiconducting materials [22] and is always emitted in backward direction, Čerenkov radiation leads to strong signals as soon as the Čerenkov limit [23,24] is exceeded and is emitted in the forward direction. Indeed, only back-scattered electrons which are still exceeding the Čerenkov limit do excite Čerenkov photons. It is

important to consider the electron back scatter yield (EBS), which can be calculated accordingly to [25,26]. For the present calculation we use the average atomic number of GaAs being $Z = 32$.

As a consequence, nearly every third electron is scattered backwards and – as long as its energy $E > E_{max}$ – Čerenkov photons are excited. The normalized probability for Čerenkov photon emission P_{CP} (per unit charge and unit path length) in a bulk material can be calculated [27]. When combining both, the electron back scatter yield and the Čerenkov photon emission probability, nearly every fourth electron being accelerated towards the sample surface creates a Čerenkov photon in backward direction as long as E_{max} is exceeded. Hence, Čerenkov photons contribute to the overall CL-spectrum in a significant way.

We can calculate the beam energy dependent Čerenkov intensity either by using Yamamoto’s theory [28,29] or by looking back to the roots of the description of Čerenkov radiation [4]. Fig. 1 the simulated Čerenkov photon intensity for GaAs for discrete beam energies (10, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120, 150, 200 keV) is shown, too, using Čerenkov’s description [4,23,27,30].

The Čerenkov radiation intensity increases linearly with increasing electron beam energy. We can use this knowledge for identifying its contribution to the overall CL-spectrum.

Semiconductors yield small Transition radiation intensity when irradiated by fast electrons [22], which was experimentally verified earlier [31]. The excited frequencies are in the same range as the defect state related luminescence. Because of its low intensity, it is not studied in closer detail here.

3. Experimental

It is known, that the CL spectrum of GaAs yields a characteristic peak below 900 nm which depends on several parameters, like temperature T [32], beam energy E_0 [3], time t , and electron dose rate EDR [3] as well as doping and defect levels [1,33]. High electron energies cause Čerenkov photons and change in the overall spectral shape. A limited collection angle of the mirrors influences the CL-spectrum, too, due to the different angular emission profiles of the different physical processes.

In the present work we used a 200 μm thick Czochralski grown single crystalline high-purity GaAs-wafer. A disc of 3 mm diameter was cut out of a larger wafer and subsequently it was divided into two half-discs. Such a half-disc specimen was neither ion-etched nor mechanically polished. Consequently, it was prevented from any damage or crystalline modification and can be expected as being free of any crystalline defects. It was then mounted into the CL-sample holder and inserted into our FEI TECNAI G20. This microscope can be operated at beam energies from 10 keV to 200 keV. The CL-spectrometer is a GATAN VULCAN CL detection and analysis system connected to the respective CL-sample holder (see scheme in Fig. 8) via a ThorLabs FT800EMT low-OH cable of 15 m length. The absorption behaviour, reflectivity of the mirrors, effect of blazing of the analyser and wave length dependent detection quantum efficiency of the detector were included in a spectrum correction routine. For this correction routine, a transition radiation spectrum of a poly-crystalline Aluminium specimen showing arbitrary crystal orientations was measured and compared to its theoretical counterpart.

4. Results

In Fig. 2 a CL-spectrum is shown of the 200 μm thick GaAs sample recorded with an electron dose rate of $8050 \frac{e^-}{\text{nm}^2 \cdot \text{s}}$ and a beam energy of 120 keV. We can identify three main regions, whereof the peak at 892 nm is the most prominent one. This peak is related to the electron transitions between the conduction band and the valence band referred “main interband transition” (MIBT) peak. It can be fitted by a Gaussian function. The second most prominent part of the spectrum is a background at beyond 900 nm wavelength. This part of the spectrum

Fig. 1. Left: electron back-scatter (EBS) yield for a specimen with an average atomic number $Z = 32$, calculated using Eq. 68 in [26]. Right: Simulated Čerenkov photon intensity (total visible range) in GaAs.

Fig. 2. CL-spectrum of bulk GaAs (blue) recorded with an electron dose rate of $8050 \frac{e^-}{\text{nm}^2 \cdot \text{s}}$ and a beam energy of 120 keV at IN_2 temperature decomposed into the main interband transition peak (grey), Čerenkov photons (red), and defect related intensities (green).

is called “Čerenkov photons”. The third fraction of the spectrum can be found at shorter wavelengths and is related to defect states [1,3]. These intensities can be explained in terms of non-radiative recombination processes which are coupled to Gallium vacancies and EL-2 defects [12, 34] – which are understood as arsenic anti-site defects [13]. Therefore we call this part of the spectrum further-on “defect states related photons”. For any further analysis, all recorded spectra are decomposed into these three contributions, where only the main interband transition peak is fitted by using a Gaussian function.

4.1. Variation of electron beam energy

As already mentioned, the shape of the CL-spectrum depends on many different parameters. In the present subsection we keep all parameters constant except of the beam energy. This means, that the electron dose rate, which is $8050 \frac{e^-}{\text{nm}^2 \cdot \text{s}}$ in the present set-up, and the temperature, which is room temperature, is kept constant. The recorded spectra are corrected for the spectrometer parameters and the intensity is divided by the acquisition time and beam size. That way it is guaranteed, that the only influence on shape and intensity is due to the beam energy. Fig. 3 shows the colour coded intensity of the experimental series starting at 20 keV and going up to 200 keV. The contours are equidistant and the white line shows the main interband transition maximum, which varies with beam energy, as the Čerenkov photon intensity does, too.

Fig. 3. CL-spectra of GaAs recorded at various beam energies applying constant EDR and temperature. Colour coding is arbitrary, the contours are equidistant and the white line emphasizes the interband transition maximum.

Fig. 4. Integrated intensities of the decomposed fractions of the CL-spectrum in GaAs with respect to the beam energy.

The interband transition maximum is highest for 120 keV beam energy, hence the scattering cross section is largest at this elevated energy. Decomposing the experimental results and integrating over all wavelengths shows the linear increase of the Čerenkov photon intensity, as calculated in Fig. 1. Fig. 4 shows the resulting integrated intensities with respect to the beam energy.

The wavelengths of the main interband transition (MIBT) maxima are varying, too, and are tabulated in Table 2, for room temperature (RT) and liquid Nitrogen temperature (IN_2). Between the RT and the IN_2 measurement a peak shift of 50.6 nm is observed, which is independent of the beam energy. All other results are in perfect agreement to the ones previously shown and recorded at room temperature.

Table 2
Maxima of the main interband transition peak at various beam energies E_0 and temperature.

E_0	\max_{RT} (nm)	\max_{IN_2} (nm)
20	874.7	824.1
40	880.7	830.2
80	888.6	838.0
120	891.9	841.2
160	894.0	843.5
200	896.3	845.7

Fig. 5. Integrated intensities of the total CL-spectrum and the respective Čerenkov intensities in GaAs with respect to the electron dose rate.

4.2. Variation of electron dose rate

When keeping the beam energy and the temperature constant, we can vary the electron dose rate (EDR). This can either be done by changing the condenser lens system or by varying the Wehnelt bias of the thermionic electron gun. Whereas the latter method does not alter the irradiated area of the GaAs specimen, the prior EDR variation does change it. Consequently, the detected signal has to be normalized with respect to the irradiated area and the acquisition time. In the present situation we did both and additionally we normalized the intensities such, that the Čerenkov intensity is one at the beginning of the graph. In series 1 the beam diameter was 11.7 μm , in series 2 it was 6.9 μm . Fig. 5 gives the total intensity and the Čerenkov intensity with respect to the EDR. One immediately recognizes, that the ratio between total intensity and Čerenkov intensity is nearly constant. The factor is approximately 3.2. As guide for the eye linear fits are integrated in the figure for pointing at the linear behaviour of both, the overall intensity and the Čerenkov intensity, respectively.

Beside this result, which was already expected when considering the electron back scatter yield and the Čerenkov photon emission probability, another effect is observed: the maximum of the interband transition has a blue shift with increasing EDR and its full width at half maximum (FWHM) is increasing, too. This is explained as being due to local sample heating [3]. As proof of this claim, we steadily increased the EDR from $104.1 \frac{e^-}{\text{nm}^2 \cdot \text{s}}$ to $1709 \frac{e^-}{\text{nm}^2 \cdot \text{s}}$. In the same time the maximum blue-shifted by 3 nm, the FWHM increased by 1.5 nm. Finally we set the EDR quickly back to $104.1 \frac{e^-}{\text{nm}^2 \cdot \text{s}}$ and the maximum of the main interband transition peak switched back to its initial values. The same behaviour can be observed at IN_2 temperature, but blue-shifted by 48.3 nm.

4.3. Temperature dependent spectra

When comparing GaAs spectra recorded at IN_2 and room temperature, two main differences catch ones eye. The first one is, that

the main interband transition peak is blue-shifted. Consequently, the Čerenkov spectrum is extended with respect to the increased band gap. Its intensity is not influenced, because the illumination conditions are kept constant. The second change is the intensity of the main interband transition peak. An opposite behaviour is reported by Radhakrishnan and Salviati [32], where the intensity increases with decreasing temperature. In our experiment the FWHM of the Gaussian fit of the main interband transition peak is increasing from 25 nm at RT to 32 nm at IN_2 temperature (see Fig. 6). This behaviour is also in contradiction to Radhakrishnan and Salviati.

The position of the MIBT as well as its FWHM is due to the local density of point defects, anti-site defects [33], and vacancies. Due to the condition of neutrality, being required in any semiconductor, an equilibrium of those defects has to be self tuned by the system. This equilibrium is dependent on the temperature controlled by the cooling device but varied locally by electron bombardment during the investigation.

4.4. Influence of constant electron irradiation

In order to judge, whether or not the spectral intensities in the range of wavelengths being shorter than the main interband transition peak position are due to defect states, we irradiated the 200 μm thick GaAs specimen continuously for 8 min with $1709 \frac{e^-}{\text{nm}^2 \cdot \text{s}}$ at IN_2 temperature (see Fig. 7). Every 60 s we recorded a CL spectrum with 1 s acquisition time. Astonishingly we find, that the intensity in the range of 500 nm to the interband transition peak at 838 nm does not change within the accuracy of measurement. For a better visibility, we normalized the results by dividing the single measured intensities by the mean value of the whole experimental series.

Second, we measured the intensity in the main interband transition (MIBT) peak and normalized the results such, that the experiment at the beginning of the time series shows an intensity of “1”. Hence, it is easier to observe, that the MIBT peak intensity decreases with increasing electron irradiation by 4% after 7 min. Its FWHM is 27.1747 nm. This value is extremely constant during the whole experiment. Again, for better visibility, we normalized the measured FWHMs by the mean value of the whole experimental series.

The reduction of the MIBT’s intensity is related to defect creation at the sample surface, and thus called quenching [33].

5. Discussion

We investigated experimental conditions for the CL-analysis of GaAs at elevated beam energies in a scanning (transmission) electron microscope. From our calculations and experiments we can conclude, that the overall shape of the CL spectrum is influenced by the beam energy, the creation of anti-site and point defects, and the Čerenkov intensity. The wavelength of the main interband transition is dependent on the local temperature of the specimen area under electron irradiation, and thus depends on the electron dose rate. For SEM-CL the excitation of Čerenkov radiation is in general not significant, since only rarely elevated beam energies are employed. On the other hand, in STEM-CL elevated beam energies are used in order to have a better spatial resolution. In this situation Čerenkov radiation is significant.

The CL-sample holder consists of two high-grade polished elliptical Aluminium mirrors (top and bottom mirror) shown in purple colour in Fig. 8, which are asymmetric with respect to the y -axis but symmetric with respect to the x -axis. The specimen is mounted in one focal point of the mirrors, hence the emitted light is reflected into the second focal point, where it is collected by the light guides — shown in light blue. This asymmetry has a consequence when detecting light being emitted with certain angular emission profiles, as being discussed later within the present work. The azimuthal collection angle is of the GATAN VULCAN is 180° , whereas the altitude is between 21° and 63° .

Fig. 6. CL spectra of bulk GaAs at 200 keV at room temperature (RT) and IN₂ temperature exhibit maxima at 896.3 nm and 845.7 nm, respectively. The insets show temperature dependent maxima at 875 nm (213 K), 878.4 nm (228 K), 828 nm (243 K), and 889.4 nm (268 K), respectively. Both, the FWHM and the central wave length are following universal curves (black full lines), being a property of GaAs. The central wavelength of the MIBT follows $\lambda_{centr.}(T) = 890 + 0.26 \cdot T$, the FWHM of the MIBT is $FWHM(T) = 25 - 0.03 \cdot T$.

Fig. 7. Normalized intensity of defect related states, main interband transition peak, and FWHM of the main interband transition peak with respect to the time of electron irradiation.

Consequently, the light collection efficiency depends on the direction into which the photons are emitted.

We quantified the spectral components with respect to the beam position. The beam was moved by $\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$ in steps of $50 \mu\text{m}$ in x - and y -direction indicated in Fig. 8. The y -direction points out of the mirror plane and is the direction perpendicular to the mirror plane projected onto the sample plane. The x -direction is perpendicular to the y -direction in the plane of the sample. The intensities of the Čerenkov photons and of the defect related emission was set into relation to first the MIBT peak intensity, and second these intensities were set into relation to each other. We found, that the ratio of Čerenkov photon intensity over defect related intensity is constant over the whole area of investigation, whereas the ratio of the MIBT peak intensity over the defect related or Čerenkov photons is strongly dependent on the beam position. Additionally, the asymmetry of the mirrors along the y -axis can be clearly seen.

This asymmetry of the detection system has a significant consequence: as soon as the angle of incidence changes (due to rough sample surfaces or a wedge shaped specimen) the emission behaviour of light is also strongly influenced. Hence, a quantitative information is difficult to obtain from CL-spectra.

Another important aspect of CL-experiments is related to the asymmetry of the mirrors. As soon as the position of measurement is not

Fig. 8. Left: Scheme of the GATAN VULCAN CL-sample holder (adopted from [35]), e – electron beam, s – sample, m – mirror, w – wave guide. Right: Beam position dependent intensity distribution. Green curve: MIBT (mean interband transition) peak intensity over Čerenkov photon intensity, blue curve: MIBT peak intensity over defect related photon intensity, and red curve: Čerenkov photon intensity over defect related photon intensity.

exactly in the mirrors focal point, not only the collection efficiency decreases, but also the spectral shape changes. This is because the CL spectrum is a composition of light stemming from various physical processes, each with its particular angular emission behaviour.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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